

High ECTS- Credit Module in Education in the System Study _ Process Organize, Students _ Knowledge of Assessment Criteria

Madaminov Furkatjon Shukhratjonovich

Teacher of the department Fine and Applied Arts, Namangan state university

Abstract:

This article provides information on the organization of the educational process based on the ECTS-credit module in the higher education system, the evaluation of student knowledge based on the rating, and the methodology of evaluating student knowledge.

Keywords: ECTS credit-module system, person, science, national program, education, experience, educational load, academic hours, technology, independent research, evaluation criterion, rating, methodology, conversion, syllabus.

INTRODUCTION

At the stage of technical development of society, the sharp increase in information and the limitation of time to use it in the process of education and training , as well as the need for a new approach to our education system to perfectly prepare the future generation for life, the content, goals and tasks of education expanding , causing its forms and methods to be renewed. Based on the need for such a new approach, it is appropriate to adapt the methodology of student assessment and educational technologies to our national educational system based on the ECTS credit-module system, making extensive use of the experience of practical application of pedagogical educational technologies of developed countries. Modern teaching technology, equipment of the higher education institution, the composition of professors and teachers consisting only of highly qualified personnel, high quality of teaching are the initial requirements of ECTS. [1]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on the combination of module technologies of education and credit measurement. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. According to the ECTS credit-module curriculum: All academic subjects are divided into two groups - subjects based on compulsory and student's choice. [2]

Study _ science of the program content (syllabus) as follows own into takes :

- study _ _ of science complete to be named and his study in the plan order number ;
- study _ science learning purpose ;
- study _ science briefly content ;
- calendar plan , training _ schedule with _
- study _ technology ;
- of students responsibility and to him placed _ requirements ;
- students knowledge evaluation order and criteria ;
- main and additional _ books list _ [3]

EC TS credit - in the module teaching _ of the process basis: To the person directed teaching technologies organize is enough ; Student's independent at work teacher consultant as participation is enough ; A student study science and the teacher choose to the right have _ Each _ to the student information package is given , it is the following own _ into takes:

Olya education institution about information; study _ plan; study of the process graph; study of sciences content; higher education in the institution acceptance done education system Methodical features about information; students knowledge evaluation system and grades cool about information; social - household to conditions belongs to information; historical and cultural to the field about information; addition education services about data. [4]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the credit-module principle, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating. Student assessment is conditionally divided into 2 parts: initial assessment and main assessment.

1. Initial assessment.

- ✓ Supervision of lecture training.
- ✓ Control of practical, experimental training.
- ✓ Independent educational supervision.
- ✓ Control of KI, KL, HGI.

2. Basic assessment. The student will pass the final control of the subject, in which at least 60% of the correct answers will be evaluated positively. [5]

In chapter 5 of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 359 of June 10, 2021, evaluation and conversion of evaluations were discussed separately. [6]

Students knowledge evaluation methodology

Study _ process credit technology based on organize most of them 4 points in cases grades scale support , 100% evaluation system is used .

For example : A-4; B-3.5 b; C-3 b; D -2.5 b; E-2 b; FY-1, 5 b, F-1 b.

100% rating system as follows distribution can : to training participation - 5%, current testing -30%, usually 3 times from 10%; independent things execution -15%, on average 3 times from 5%; laboratory their work execution -10%, course execution of the project (work) -10%; final exam - 30%. Below to be brought grades 100% evaluation of criteria in the system when used use can _

Evaluation criteria

Grades tariff	Conditional sign	Mastery % _	Evaluation criterion	Preparation level
Excellent	A	90-100	Knowledge summarizes and evaluates, analysis is enough understands, knows.	Level 4: creativity degree
Very good	B	80-90 analysis	Analysis does , applies , understands , knows _	Level 3 : Skill and qualification level (automatic)
Good	C	70-80 application _	Uses , understands , knows _	Level 3 : Skill and qualification degree
Satisfactory	D	60-70 understanding	He understands , he knows	2nd level : re recovery level
Enough	E	Know 50-60	He knows	Level 1: Imagination reach level
Enough not , extra _ again work is required	FY	40-50	It's bad knows	Level 0: bad imagination is enough
Enough not , extra _ again too many _ work is required .	OF	40 less	In general doesn't know	Level 0: at all imagination can't

Study _ science 90-100% mastery of the material “excellent” grade right will come. This is the 4th level of preparation equalized and defines the level of “creativity “.

Study _ “adequate” grade when at least 50% of the science program is mastered is put, this

“master _ imagination level is defined as ” . Study _ less than 40% of science mastery 0 level of preparation, i.e. “at all imagination it is considered “not enough “.

100 percent evaluation system students knowledge evaluation cool for conditions creates _ [7]

Summary

Education efficiency in raising assessment right _ to the road to put from the pedagogue skill and requires skill. _ Evaluation this student for please _ and motivation is considered Teacher this in progress innovative approaching justice criterion based on evaluate the student person as to himself trust in the spirit educates , freely independent thinking personnel to cultivate service does _

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